

Professional Development of Teachers – A Rating Scale on Self-Assessment of Teacher Educators for Professional Development

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ABSTRACT

Abstract— improving teacher quality is at the heart of our national effort to achieve excellence in the classroom. This comes at a time when the very structure of education is going through a profound change and recognition of wide differences when teacher education institutions will help teachers understand the strengths and weaknesses of their education in planning for their professional future. It is the professional growth that a teacher achieves as a result of gaining increased experience and examining his/her teaching systematically. The author has thus prepared a rating scale on self-assessment of teacher educators on professional development. The components selected are Enhancing Teacher Effectiveness, Transference of knowledge through innovative models and Trends, Prediction of Teacher Morale, Professional Ethics, Technology as a back- up force in professional development and Teaching Styles. The tool has been validated by experts and a pilot study has been made to find out the reliability of the tool. The reliability is 0.78 and the test is highly reliable. The paper is concluded with educational implications related to enhancing quality in professional development of teacher educators.

Keywords—Teacher Effectiveness, Transference of knowledge through innovative models and trends, Prediction of Teacher Morale, Professional Ethics, Technology as a back-up force, Teaching Styles

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is one of the oldest profession, but the role, functions and preparations of teachers undergo changes from time to time according to society’s expectations. The paper reflects on the professional development needs of teacher educators with reference to the role of institutions of teacher education. Improving teacher quality is at the heart of our national effort to achieve excellence in the classroom. The current focus is on the development of professional competencies, commitment and motivation for higher level performance. With knowledge all around us, available

“Contemporary Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education”

anytime and anywhere the role of the teacher is going to be fundamentally transformed in the 21st century.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Most of the students preferred to be taught by dedicated and qualified teachers who can provide quality education for them as said by Lal, K., & Paul, S. The study revealed that graduate and post graduate primary school teachers were effective in their teaching as said by Topno, I., & Kumar, D. The article explained by Haydn, Terry gives various aspects for assessing the teachers for professionalism. The case study conducted revealed that for a successful learning community a felt inclusion in all domains is very important as referred by J. W. Creswell.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Striving towards improving education will ascend or descend based on the quality of teaching and the defining role in preparing the next generation teachers is taken up by higher education. The teacher institutions thus are motivated to contribute to the quality of education in the classroom and the main purpose lies in producing teachers with professional competencies. To determine professionalism one needs to equip with intellectual tendencies, acquire opportunities for various skills and abilities, generate and set its own standards, generate desire for service than personal gain and to possess strong professional organisation behind it.

Enhancement is a process of augmentation or improvement. In relation to higher education quality enhancement refers to the enhancement of individual learners; the augmentation or improvement of learners' attributes, knowledge, ability, skills and potential and also the improvement in the quality of an institution or programme of study. Hence, in this research paper, the author has explained about the preparation of a tool for enhancing quality in a teacher educator through professional development.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY:

To construct and validate a Rating Scale on Self-Assessment of Teacher Educators for Professional Development

DESCRIPTION OF THE TOOL

Professional Development of Teacher Educators

Professional Development refers to skills and knowledge attained for both personal development and career advancement. It is the professional growth a teacher achieves as a result of gaining

increased experience and examining his/her teaching systematically. And here below are seven components that contribute to the success of professional development of a teacher educator.

1. Enhancing Teacher Effectiveness

Teacher effectiveness is the first layer in which teachers’ characteristics, including beliefs and competencies could be enhanced through training and professional development. The characteristics of Teacher effectiveness are:

- Personal characteristics of teachers – This includes features of teachers’ personality such as flexibility/rigidity, extraversion/introversion, self-efficacy, general and verbal intelligence.
- Pedagogical content knowledge – described as deep knowledge of subject matter for teaching and students’ prior knowledge.
- Teacher beliefs and competencies – This focuses on the behavioural repertoire of teachers than on deeply rooted aspects of their personality. This includes clusters such as (i) Professionalism (ii) Thinking/ reasoning – analytical thinking and conceptual thinking , (iii) Expectations – Drive for improvement, information seeking and initiative (iv) Leadership – flexibility, accountability and passion for learning
- Teacher’s sense of efficacy –level of competence a person expects he/she will display in a given situation.

2. Transference of knowledge through innovative models and trends

Teachers need a deep and flexible understanding of subject matter and how to represent ideas so that they are accessible to others. For this they need to develop content knowledge, pedagogical knowledge and understanding of the unique features of learners. The new trends for enhancing quality include:

- Interdisciplinary approach (Problem of isolation with other disciplines), Internship, community services, orientation courses.
- Mechanism of feedback devices for modification of teacher behaviour – simulated teaching, micro teaching, programmed instruction
- Team teaching, supervised study, supplementary reading, Action research, Use of Laboratories
- New trends also focus on offline learning, e-learning, video conferencing, virtual classroom, reflective teaching, and system approach.

3. Prediction of Teacher Morale

Concept of ‘morale’ includes key components such as enthusiasm, dedication, a common shared goal and unification. High morale of teachers creates a more pleasant environment for students. This includes perceptions related to academic climate, social climate, physical and administrative climate.

4. Professional Ethics

Professionally accepted standards of personal and work behaviour, values and guiding principles are called Code of professional ethics and are often established by professional organizations to help guide members in performing their job functions according to sound and consistent ethical principles.

5. Technology as a back- up force in professional development

Technology has the potential to transform the professional environment for educators. It influences two aspects of education. The teacher training institutions can train prospective teachers (pre-service) and second the institutions can design continuing education for teachers to learn their job at the workplace. This includes: Teacher training curricula, students to be trained in basic skills, access to computers and internet and integrating ICT in teaching and learning.

6. Teaching Styles

Teaching style refers to the teaching strategies and methods employed and the use of ‘a set of teaching tactics’. These strategies are determined partly on subject matter to be taught and by the nature of the learner and consists of the dimensions such as:

- Participation in the learning process – This represents those enduring personal qualities and behaviours that appear in how the teacher conducts class
- Relating to experience- an understanding of various skills and learning styles that students’ possess
- Climate building -create a learning environment through using of gestures, voice modulation and similar activities that stimulate learning
- Learner centered activities – planning activities according to the preferences in learning styles of students
- Personalizing instruction – The teacher plans identifies a set of classroom behaviors for

his/her own personal growth

7. Self-Reflective Learning

This means making a self- assessment of oneself. In this approach the teacher educator and student reflects on the experience in the form of teaching leaning tasks performed and practices carried out. This involves:

- Peer review and discussion – views of peers and fellow professionals
- Feedback in form of attitudes and feelings, experience and knowledge.
 - a. Steps in the construction of the Rating Scale

CONSTRUCTION OF THE RATING SCALE

The rating scale was constructed under the following phases.

- Phase 1: Identification of the components of Professional development of teacher educators
Going through related literature, journals and internet about professional development of teachers and quality assurance in higher education, the author identified the above seven components.
- Phase 2: Writing of items
The author prepared a rating scale with 105 items to make a self- assessment of teacher educators. Each component was given equal weightage and statements were to be rated on a four point scale.
- Phase 3: Preparation of the Initial draft
The rating scale was submitted to the experts for initial evaluation. The experts checked for specificity, language, relevance and comprehensiveness and gave their suggestions as: irrelevant statements to be deleted, restructuring negative statements, focusing more on operational definitions of the components.
The feedback was incorporated and the number of statements was brought down to 75. Thus the content validity of the tool was ascertained. The author added the instructions to be followed by the sample and the items were arranged in a systematic manner.
- Phase 4: Validation of the Initial draft
This was further given to experts in the field and the following aspects were considered for improvement in the tool – clarity, relevance, precision, variety and objectivity. The experts

“Contemporary Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education”

suggested avoiding two ideas in a single statement, statements need to be specific and short and the first component to be restructured.

- Phase 5: Preparation of the second draft

The tool was redrafted. The numbers of items were reduced to sixty. Care was taken to check whether the statements were able to assess professional development of teacher educators.

- Phase 6: Pilot administration

The tool was administered to a sample of forty teacher educators from different colleges to determine the feasibility of how successful the tool is and check the practicability of the components. The observations made during the pilot testing were: some of the statements were of higher order and difficult to answer; the teachers took 15-20 minutes to answer; there was considerable inconsistency in the ratings to some items; few items belonging to the fifth component had to re-word.

- Phase 7: Final draft of the Rating Scale

This consisted of 60 items which intended to make a self-assessment of teacher educators regarding their professional development. The respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which statement is satisfying by rating it on a four point scale. A highest of 240 scores could be achieved by a person. The weightage given to the selected items is given in Table 1

**TABLE 1
WEIGHTAGE GIVEN TO THE COMPONENTS**

Component	Positive statements	Negative statements	No.of items	%age
1.	1,2,3,4,5,6	7,8,9	9	15.0%
2.	10,11,12,13,14,15	16,17	8	13.33%
3.	18,19,20,21,22,23	24,25	8	13.33%
4.	26,27,28,29,30,31	32,33	8	13.33%
5.	34,35,36,37,38,39	40,41,42	9	15%
6.	43,44,45,46,47,48,49, 50	51,52	10	16.68%
7.	53,54,55,56,57,58	59,60	8	13.33%
Total	44	16	60	100%

Establishing Validity of the Tool

Content validity that refers to examining appropriateness of test items is explained under phase

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three. The author developed the content validity by taking into consideration the opinion of the experts for examining the appropriateness of each of the statements. The Face Validity that pertains to immediate judgement of the tool in terms of content is explained under phase 4.

Estimating Reliability of the Tool

The reliability was established on a sample of 40 teacher educators. The Split-half Reliability method was adopted. The procedure for adopted for determining Split-half Reliability is as follows:

- Administration of total tool to a sample (N=40)
- Dividing statements into two equal halves with odd numbered statements into one half and even numbered statements into second half.
- Computing each teacher’s scores on two halves of the test.
- Correlating the two sets of scores
- Evaluating the result

The correlation between the two sets of scores was found to be 0.72 and was a strong correlation. From the reliability of half test, the correlation of the whole tool was estimated by Spearman-Brown Prophecy formula.

The reliability was found to be 0.78 which indicates the tool constructed by the author was highly reliable.

A Rating Scale on Self-Assessment of Teachers for Professional Development

Instructions

Dear Teacher,

As I am writing an article on ‘Professional Development in Teacher Education’, here is a tool on ‘Self-Assessment of Teachers for Professional Development’ as a part of the same. The data collected would be highly confidential in this regard. The rating scale consists of 60 items. The following statements pertain to different domains of teacher assessment for which you are requested to indicate the extent to which you find them satisfying. Each statement is to be evaluated on a 4-point scale. Please indicate your response against each statement in the manner given below: To A Great Extent (GE) -4, Moderate Extent (ME)-3, Some Extent (SE) -2 and Not

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At All (NA) -1. Please put a tick mark on your response which you will evaluate as an opinion about yourself as a teacher educator.

Statements	4	3	2	1
1.My presentations have clarity adapted to suit the cognitive level of pupils				
2.I organize academic activities with enthusiasm				
3.I direct pupils in task related behaviors				
4.I accept pupils’ ideas in any activities				
5.I have the skill of varying the level of cognitive interaction among pupils				
6.I use creative strategies to meet the classroom expectations				
7.My criticism has a negative effect on student achievement				
8.I am paid less in comparison with the quantum of work allotted				
9.I shoulder responsibility only with the colleagues whom I like.				
10.I attend workshops to strengthen my knowledge of my discipline				
11.I give opportunities for reflection in the classroom				
12.I enjoy regular collaboration with interdisciplinary teams for academic work				
13.I feel it is important for a teacher educator to be aware of new trends for professional development				
14.My classes are mainly focused on e-learning				
15.I update myself about innovative teaching models				
16.I avoid wasting time on peer coaching				
17. Using ICT for all types of classes deprives students’ thinking ability.				
18.My job profile has enhanced my social status				
19.My institutional environment is a predictor to my success				
20.I play the role of a leader while carrying on teaching tasks				
21.I am competent in sorting out problems in the institution				

“Contemporary Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education”

22.I share pleasant environment with my students				
23.I have good communicative skills while teaching				
24.I have difficulty adjusting while working in teams				
25.Some of my colleagues try to defame me as unsuccessful				
26.I am impartial to my students.				
27.I recognize the difference in aptitude among students and try to meet their individual needs				
28.I guide my students without any remuneration or reward				
29.I inculcate scientific outlook among my students				
30.I am affectionate towards the students				
31.I manage private affairs with dignity of the profession				
32.I lodge secret complaints against colleagues to higher authorities.				
33.I feel envied by the professional growth of another colleague				
34.I train students in using technology in the classrooms				
35.I prepare short ICT based tutorials to deliver the content				
36.I have joined online study groups outside my institution to explore innovations in teaching.				
37.My institution makes use Open Educational Resources(OER) for teaching learning				
38.I plan teaching strategies using PowerPoint presentations				
39. I make use of research findings about technology while planning for educational environment.				
40.My institution lacks technology resources				
41.I feel discomfort in accessing the computer and internet				
42.I find it difficult to prepare lesson plans according to different needs of students using technology				
43.I allow each student to work at his/her own rate regardless of the amount of time it takes him/her to learn a new concept				

“Contemporary Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education”

44.I gear the instructional objectives to match the individual abilities and needs of the students while planning lessons.				
45. I help students relate new learning to their prior experiences.				
46. I help students diagnose the gaps between their goals and their present level of performance.				
47. I encourage dialogue and discussion among my students.				
48.I allow my students to take periodic breaks during the class.				
49. I rearrange the classroom so that it is easy for students to interact.				
50.I allow students to participate in developing the criteria for evaluating their performance in class.				
51.I find it difficult to use variety of teaching methods				
52. I discourage students to ask questions while teaching.				
53.I provide adequate learning experiences in my classroom				
54.I consider the suggestions and implement them in my lessons				
55.My potential to perform as a teacher educator is better than the previous year				
56.I spend time reflecting about any task accomplished.				
57.I am contented with my teaching profession				
58.My aim is to serve as a positive role model to students				
59.I am not concerned with pupils’ feedback				
60. I perceive my profession as a place of ‘employment’ rather than ‘rendering service’.				

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS

- A sound programme of professional education of teachers enhances the qualitative improvement of education. This could be done through:
- Providing opportunities for active teaching and academic freedom in teacher education institutions.
- Effective communication and participatory decision making among staff and other officials in the institution as well as with students.

“Contemporary Issues and Challenges of Teacher Education”

- Well-equipped staff room, seating arrangements in the staff room. Decreasing class size improves sociability, extracurricular participation and academic achievements.
- Supervision of especially academic research and extension activities and social behavior of teacher educators.
- A dynamic and trustworthy institutional climate is a predictor of success for a teacher educator.

Concluding Note

With the rapid influx of dynamic teachers in the teaching profession and the involvement of technology, the teaching skills are evolved likewise. As the future lies in the hands of us, ‘Teachers’ and their teacher educators, the professional development will reflect upon the consistent efforts made to improvise, evolve and effectively enthuse novel practices in the teaching learning process.

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